

eu4child

An Artificial Intelligence ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

Mapping the landscape of AI applications for Childhood Cancer to improve care pathways in Europe

This is us

Bringing together **clinicians**, **young cancer patients** and **AI experts**

POLITÉCNICA

HUMANITAS
RESEARCH HOSPITAL

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International Foundation
for Integrated Care
A movement for change

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